

RADIOLOGICAL EVALUATION OF EFFECTIVENESS AND COMPREHENSIVE TREATMENT GENERALIZED PERIODONTITIS

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Annotation: Complex treatment of generalized periodontitis, the special attention paid by the appropriate combination of conservative and surgical treatment methods, significantly increases the destructive process of the connective tissue and restoring the amount of available data[1-9]. However, despite the variety of facts and developments, conservative and surgical interventions on the nexus alone cannot clearly read the disease process and sufficient condition of the gum tissue regeneration[10-18]. Cases, the use of new technologies, including the use of medical rehabilitation, medical wipes and other conservative treatment, did not lead or the underlying mechanism of the inflammatory process, and case affect its further destruction. Consultation with stakeholders lesions 2-3 degrees of severity, the bones of an existing connection. Commission staff working different items of the truth, there no real medical research hospital with symptoms of the disease, which created a course solve the protein content of conservative treatment and the active process of destruction of abnormal bone tissue.

Purpose of the work:. Terms of conservative and surgical treatment of common cardiovascular examination system requirements and 2-3 degrees described herein.Hospital x-ray performed 123 hospital with extensive lesions of the aged 18-64 12 months. All prospective divided into 2 age groups: the first group included the hospital with 2-3 students study diabetes aged 18 39 (n=58), and the second group included the hospital with 2-3 students study diabetes aged 40 64 (n=65).. Evaluated the clinical and radiological parameters based on a sample of a

research between the age groups and subgroups, so that, on the age and clinical features of disease development of atherosclerosis. Depending on the nature of the disease, a comprehensive treatment plan interventions include: workplace mouth rehabilitation; therapeutic shower hormones (0.05 million folic acid, etc.)).) And anti-inflammatory cytokines gum tissue. According the definition, organisms antioxidant, anti-inflammatory treatment with nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, chemicals and tubular bones of the performance. The procedure includes the necessary plastic surgery, sterile, and disposable masks. The bones of the false positive reduction . Results and discussion. During the investigation, the prerogative of mercy health 18-39-12 months -old health group gum ache, blood (sometimes multiple), separated by a leisure activity or dinner, necrotic tissue during the inflammatory process, reduce the impact load conditions when determining eligibility. The involvement of these groups from the moment the medical treatment of the disease, it takes from 3 10 12 months. Based on medical history, prior medical compression treatment, health remedies company MD. This case, the treatment method by adding staff accounting and stopped several times. Because of personnel shortages, the hospital system spread. The next message after consultation with the pressure of disease, none of the clinical studies under the observation of health. Scientific studies have shown that hospital with severe symptoms of degree 2 and 3 of this age group not quick bite prevention as well. Maple TA index 3.9-0.4, and the involvement with 3-4 members of the bones of the Ada and the camera has the advantage of medical advances. Preparation characterized by a high degree of bone mentally. Broad fungal compartment ranged from 6 of 10 cubic meters.Laboratory studies, bone defects often the best size of the skull. On clinical examination the mouth clavier, book hospital with severe symptoms noted the presence of a fault still have pie, Unpasteurize certain diseases. The case, could widen the mouth of something complicated (especially the posterior region of the lower jaw), the duration of the postoperative mean bone and stomach

region of the upper jaw decreases rapidly, and principles of symptoms of benign prostatic development occurs. Clinical observation of consultations with stakeholders insufficient 40-64 12 months shows that the great mercy of this group of hospitals associated with the root cause, bleeding gums, weak breathing, loss of bone changes, and medical errors. The load condition of this group when seeking professional help ranged from 8 20 12 months. Action research bugs shows that the population has a fungal infection with symptoms similar deficiencies identified a younger audience, and that a systemic fungal infection associated with significant structure of soft tissues. Elderly nutrition rich medical branch . A large number of passages located behind the lower jaw. Strengthen bones holder small, increase bone loss high, and mentally bones very high. The figure shows a very common health condition which condition age-related or disease (because of severe development of cardiovascular diseases), and mesenchymal stromal inflammatory process of unknown cause overheating. Specifically, the end result of this case the progress of the disease cavernous sinus bone area 21.23 bones. This community health assessment not uncommon surgical treatment indications. Based on the medical history of the study of health, obstetric care not considered an integral part of a comprehensive drug or 96% of the hospitals early stages of treatment, and sometimes the terms of the return shipping policy prescriptions. Because of all the hospitals who don't receive comprehensive obstetric care quite high, this can help the health of distraction osteogenesis with the high tail of the upper jaw, finding like-minded people, and also consider changing the tail of the upper jaw. This case, try the incredibly impressed. It could suggest that caused the loss of strong arms bones of the upper jaw causing the symptoms and not the development of atherosclerosis. 2 study group had a high clinical index, indicating poor mouth health of different age groups. The introduction of the red - green index values of young people shows that the plates index significantly higher than the gluten index, but the inverse relationship found an old hospital. It further concerns of older

people. Other times, blood indices significantly higher among clinical younger than 12 weeks of age, and diabetes mellitus and inflammatory conditions of the most high. Adult supervision, warts naturally pale lilac color, with diabetes mellitus and the inherent tension of the soft tissues. Ultimately, this because of the lack of deep carbon remains. As adults, the average depth of the wart tissue small. The old hospital, Barker hanger dividers significantly higher . Moreover, with the preliminary results of a clinical examination and x-ray clinic with 1 and 2 academic standards of diabetes by age 40 64 12 months, it can conclude that the risk appetite assessment of long-term disease process. Age group-during this time, the mouth of the prevention of the proliferation of the oldest distilled health, but the same time, a lower immune response occurs. This permission allows the x-rays. The youngest age group involvement, severe bone destruction, aggressive actions syndrome, osteogenesis imperfecta released from 1/2 1/2 root length, breadth of the bone marrow, multiple bone bag 3). A community consultation with extensive lesions on x-ray, although the symptoms described, bone regeneration and mixed-type can perform, which combines the horizontal and vertical joint inflammatory processes. With a complex of vitamins, changing the sign indicating the condition of the elastic tissue shows the total population of consultations between 6 and 12 months after the end of treatment. With or without surgical intervention, the results of treatment are evaluated separately. After conservative treatment, the patient determines the depth of the periodontal sac, the degree of movement of the teeth and the presence of dental plates. Diagnostic indicators are used to study periodontitis: periodontal indicators (Russell, 1956), Schiller Pisarev test, PMA indicators (S.Parma, 1960), indicators of blood circulation and gingival inclination. Oral hygiene is evaluated based on the Dna method. а. Федорова и в. В. (1970) and S. et al.I.Dr.Green,J.Zinnoberfläche (1964) Since conservative treatment smoothes movable teeth, the mobility of teeth after treatment is completed has not been studied. Immediately after the end of conservative treatment, patients with

generalized periodontitis from the p-sh degree showed an improvement in the Syrah-Pisarev test results (1.97 g0.15 for patients with primary care level II and 2.11 g0.17 for patients with Gp III). An increase in the level of oral hygiene was observed (S.Green, J."I don't know," he said. The PMA index and other periodontal values tend to decrease. At the same time, according to the results of the X-ray examination, the depth of the bone bag does not change. Indicators of bleeding and suppuration changed in the direction of improvement. Generally speaking, the periodontal condition of patients with general practitioner levels II-III immediately after the end of conservative treatment is characterized by remission of the underlying disease, which is mainly associated with poor oral hygiene. The condition of periodontal tissues after 6 months after the end of conservative treatment is characterized by an increase in the Schiller-Pisarev sample and bleeding from the gums. Clinically, in the distant period after the end of conservative treatment, all indicators deteriorated. A significant loss of bone tissue was detected in the pathological bone bag region of alveolar growth, when radiological indicators of the state of the periodontal period removed after the end of conservative treatment were analyzed. In some cases, the formation of bone tissue defects is observed through the alveolar process. The following radial disorders are observed in the lower jaw: in contrast to the upper jaw, mixed bone atrophy of the alveolar process is observed in the lower jaw. In particular, bone atrophy at the SH-1 level was observed in the frontal lobe region. Sh-1u mobile class 12.11, 21 teeth were reconstructed and another 12 mobile teeth removed before treatment with the binding system began. The splint is equipped with 22 missing tooth stations bare bridge prosthesis. Another condition may be observed on the outside of the lower jaw. Bone atrophy is characterized mainly by the formation of vertical depressions of a large depth (more than 4 mm). At the same time, the focus of bone destruction is caused by an obvious chronic pericarditis process in the area of 48 teeth, 48 reserved teeth, and the remote roots of 47

teeth. The clinical situation in this case is exacerbated by the formation of additional bone sacs in area 47. Teeth that protrude beyond the root of the tooth. In area 46. The tooth is determined by the vertical bone sac in the region of the distal root of the tooth, in addition, vertical absorption of bone is observed in the region of 46 bristles. Gigi Clinically, these teeth are not moving. A similar situation can be seen in the left lower jaw. At the same time, x-rays actually reflect the condition of the right lower jaw, except for retention and dystopia48.

Conclusion:

1. Rehabilitation of patients with systemic globular palliditis must be carried out with the compulsory participation of globular pallidologists, orthopedic dentists and orthopedic dentists at all stages of treatment.

2. Taking into account the depth and intensity of the pathological process, with the compulsory participation of hygienists and gynecologists, outpatient monitoring is required at least 6 times in 1 month.

3. Conservative treatment and dental scales do not provide a truly stable pathological process in generalized periodontitis n degrees and in some cases contribute to the asymptomatic development of bone tissue destruction.

4. Surgical intervention, in which pathologically altered tissues are removed from the bone sac, replaced by bone conduction material and used in combination with other treatments, helps to reduce the breaking strength of bone tissue and in some cases creates conditions for the regeneration of periodontal tissues.

Reference:

1. Абдуллаева П. Р., Ахмедов А. А. СПОСОБ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ИШЕМИЧЕСКИХ СОСТОЯНИЙ ЗРИТЕЛЬНОГО НЕРВА И СЕТЧАТКИ (ЛИТЕРАТУРНЫЙ ОБЗОР): Medical science //Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research. – 2023. – Т. 10. – №. 09. – С. 18-23.

2. Ризаев Ж. А., Ахмедов А. А. ОСНОВЫ СТОМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПОМОЩИ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН НА ОСНОВЕ РАЗВИТИЯ ОБЩЕЙ ВРАЧЕБНОЙ ПРАКТИКИ //ЖУРНАЛ СТОМАТОЛОГИИ И КРАНИОФАЦИАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 3.

3. Абдуллаева Н. И., Ахмедов А. А. ОСТЕО-ИММУНОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ СТАТУС ПАЦИЕНТОВ С ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ ПАРОДОНТА В ПОДРОСТКОВОМ И МОЛОДОМ ВОЗРАСТЕ //TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 143-149.

4. Ахмедов А. А. Иммунологические аспекты патогенеза гингивита и пародонтита //IQRO. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 121-123.

5. Ризаев Ж. А., Ахмедов А. А. GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT OF GENERAL MEDICAL PRACTICE IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN TO IMPROVE DENTAL CARE //ЖУРНАЛ СТОМАТОЛОГИИ И КРАНИОФАЦИАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 3.

6. Ахмедов А. А., Нарзиева Н. DENTAL PROSTHETICS ON IMPLANTS AND THEIR FEATURES //American Journal of Pedagogical and Educational Research. – 2023. – Т. 16. – С. 132-135.

7. Astanovich A. D. A. et al. The State of Periodontal Tissues in Athletes Engaged in Cyclic Sports //Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology. – 2021. – С. 235-241.

8. Alimjanovich R. J., Astanovich A. A. СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ СТОМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПОМОЩИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНОГО ПОДХОДА ДЛЯ УЛУЧШЕНИЕ ЕЕ КАЧЕСТВА //JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE. – 2023. – Т. 8. – №. 4.

9. Ортикова Н. Глобализация биоэтики в период пандемии COVID-19 //Общество и инновации. – 2020. – Т. 1. – №. 1/S. – С. 677-682.
10. Ортикова Н. Влияние психоэмоционального напряжения детей на состояние здоровья полости рта //Общество и инновации. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 7/S. – С. 328-333.
11. Ортикова Н. Х., Ризаев Ж. А., Мелибаев Б. А. ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ПОСТРОЕНИЯ СТОМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ПРИЕМА ПАЦИЕНТОВ ДЕТСКОГО ВОЗРАСТА //EDITOR COORDINATOR. – 2021. – С. 554.
12. Ортикова Н. Тенденция эффективности профилактических мероприятий путем коррекции психологического стресса у детей на стоматологическом приёме //Общество и инновации. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 181-189.
13. Qobilovna B. Z., Nodirovich E. A. EVALUATION OF ORTHOPEDIC TREATMENT WITH REMOVABLE DENTAL PROSTHESES FOR PATIENTS WITH PAIR PATHOLOGY //Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development. – 2023. – Т. 11. – С. 95-101.
14. Anvarovich E. S., Qobilovna B. Z. INFLUENCE OF DIFFERENT TYPES OF RETRACTION THREADS ON THE DEGREE OF GINGI RECESSION //Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development. – 2023. – Т. 11. – С. 84-86.
15. Tohirovna M. L., Qobilovna B. Z. Optimization of Complex Methods Treatment of Inflammatory Periodontal Diseases //Eurasian Research Bulletin. – 2023. – Т. 17. – С. 138-143.

16. Tavakalova Q. M., Qobilovna B. Z., Sarvinoz Y. Preventive Measures in the Treatment of Caries in School children //Eurasian Research Bulletin. – 2023. – Т. 17. – С. 60-65.

17. Исламова Н., Чакконов Ф. Роль продуктов перекисного окисления липидов и противовоспалительных цитокинов крови в развитии заболеваний полости рта при гипотиреозе //Общество и инновации. – 2020. – Т. 1. – №. 1/с. – С. 577-582.

18. Fakhridin C., Shokhruh S., Nilufar I. ENDOKANAL PIN-KONSTRUKSIYALARNI ISHLATISHDA ASORATLAR VA XATOLAR TAHLILI //JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE. – 2022. – Т. 7. – №. 1.

19. Shoxrux S., Shoxrux I., Faxriddin C. PREVENTION AND TREATMENT OF ORAL INFECTIONS IN DENTURE WEARERS //International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education. – 2022. – Т. 14. – №. 4.

20. Xusanovich C. F. COMPLETE REMOVABLE PROSTHESIS SUPPORTED BY IMPLANTS //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 127-133.

21. Xusanovich C. F. et al. PROSTHETICS A COMPLETE REMOVABLE PROSTHESIS BASED ON IMPLANTS //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 122-126.

22. Najmiddinovich S. N. et al. CARIES IN SCHOOL CHILDREN AND TREATMENT PREVENTIVE MEASURES //American Journal of Pedagogical and Educational Research. – 2023. – Т. 16. – С. 44-49.

23. Khusanovich K. B. R. C. F. TYPES AND APPLICATIONS OF DENTAL COMPLIMENTS //Journal of Modern Educational Achievements. – 2023. – T. 5. – №. 5. – C. 95-99.

24. Zarnigor J. MAIN ROLE OF HYGIENIC EDUCATION IN THE SYSTEM PRIMARY PREVENTION OF DENTAL DISEASES OF PATIENT //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2023. – T. 3. – №. 11. – C. 157-163.

25. Qizi J. Z. B. METHODS OF OPTIMIZATION OF TREATMENT OF PERIODONTAL DISEASES USING NEW TECHNOLOGIES //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2023. – T. 3. – №. 10. – C. 234-241.

26. Kobilovna B. Z., Rushana R. COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF PARTIAL DENTURES WITH VARIOUS FASTENING ELEMENTS //Intent Research Scientific Journal. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 9. – C. 98-103.

27. Qobilovna B. Z., Maxzuna U. Improvement of Providing Therapeutic Dental Care to Pregnant Women. Therapeutic and Preventive Measures //Eurasian Research Bulletin. – 2023. – T. 16. – C. 146-150.

28. Tavakalova Q. M., Qobilovna B. Z., Sarvinoz Y. Results of the Prevention Program Dental Diseases in School-Age Children //Eurasian Research Bulletin. – 2023. – T. 17. – C. 50-54

29. Jurabek T. D., Qobilovna B. Z. Principles of Prevention of Dental Diseases in Children in Modern Conditions //Eurasian Research Bulletin. – 2023. – T. 17. – C. 55-59.

30. Tavakalova Q. M., Qobilovna B. Z., Sarvinoz Y. Preventive Measures in the Treatment of Caries in School children //Eurasian Research Bulletin. – 2023. – T. 17. – C. 60-65